

Fungal biomass and microbial necromass facilitate soil carbon sequestration and aggregate stability under different soil tillage intensities

Orracha Sae-Tun^{a,*}, Gernot Bodner^b, Christoph Rosinger^{a,b}, Sophie Zechmeister-Boltenstern^a, Axel Mentler^a, Katharina Keiblinger^a

^a Institute of Soil Research, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna, BOKU, Peter-Jordan-Straße, 1190 Vienna, Austria

^b Institute of Agronomy, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna, BOKU, Konrad-Lorenz-Straße 24, 3430 Tulln, Austria

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Agricultural soil
Fungal biomarker
Amino sugars
Soil organic carbon
Soil aggregate stability
Conservation tillage

ABSTRACT

The aim of global carbon (C) neutrality brings soils and their potential for C storage into the spotlight. Improved agricultural management techniques such as minimum or no-tillage are thought to foster soil C sequestration. However, the underlying mechanisms are still not well understood. In this study, we investigated the inter-relations of soil organic C (SOC), fungal biomass, microbial necromass biomarkers, and aggregate stability in rhizosphere and bulk soil after thirteen years of reduced tillage intensities (reduced, minimum, and no-tillage). Overall, rhizosphere and bulk soil were indifferent in their response to reduced tillage. Reducing tillage intensity increased SOC and nitrogen stocks and dissolved organic C contents in the following order: minimum > no-tillage > reduced > conventional. Aggregate stability showed the strongest increase under no-tillage. Interestingly, ergosterol contents were highest under reduced and minimum tillage followed by no-tillage. The amino sugars muramic acid, galactosamine, and glucosamine – proxies for soil microbial-derived necromass – showed similar increases under all three tillage reduction systems. Structural equation modelling revealed that increased dissolved organic C contents under reduced tillage intensity facilitated SOC sequestration and aggregate stability through enhanced fungal biomass to necromass turnover. Thus, reducing soil tillage intensity is a valuable tool to facilitate microbial growth and hence to increase SOC sequestration in agricultural soils.

1. Introduction

In recent years, the sequestration of carbon (C) into soil has increasingly received attention as a potential leverage point for current climate change mitigation strategies (Lal, 2004, 2016; Schlesinger and Amundson, 2019). As approximately one-third of the terrestrial surface is covered by agricultural land, improving agricultural management techniques towards the facilitation of soil organic C (SOC) sequestration is considered to be a valuable contribution to reaching the goal of global carbon neutrality (Haddaway et al., 2017; Minasny et al., 2017).

Conservation tillage strategies, such as non-inversion tillage or no-tillage with direct seeding, are likely to have a strong potential for enhancing SOC sequestration (Chenu et al., 2019). Several studies reported an increase in SOC contents as a result of reduced soil tillage intensity (Haddaway et al., 2017; Lal, 2013; Sanaullah et al., 2020). Six et al. (2000) proposed that an increase in SOC under no-tillage was a result of the formation of more stable soil aggregates where SOC could

be stabilized and sequestered in the long term. Indeed, there is evidence that less intensively managed and no-tilled soils exhibited higher soil aggregate stability and consequently larger SOC stocks than soils under conventional tillage which massively destructs soil aggregates and subsequently enhances C mineralization (Bartlová et al., 2015; Lal, 2013; Morris et al., 2010). The improvement of soil structure and the reduction of soil compaction and erosion risks under reduced tillage intensity prevent SOC as well as soil nutrient losses from the soil system (Blanco-Canqui and Ruis, 2018). Furthermore, less soil disturbance promotes microbial growth, particularly fungal growth, which might in turn increase the efficiency by which soil microbes utilize their C (i.e., carbon-use efficiency, CUE). A recent study demonstrated that reduced tillage intensity resulted in an increased CUE of the soil microbial community (Sauvadet et al., 2018). However, the effect of reduced tillage intensity can vary considerably and is dependent on factors such as soil type and texture, climatic conditions, the tillage system used, and time of adoption (Chenu et al., 2019; Minasny et al., 2017).

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: orrachs@students.boku.ac.at (O. Sae-Tun).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2022.104599>

Received 20 December 2021; Received in revised form 28 May 2022; Accepted 11 July 2022

Available online 19 July 2022

0929-1393/© 2022 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Soil microorganisms are pivotal drivers of terrestrial C and nitrogen (N) cycles (Liang et al., 2017; Van Der Heijden et al., 2008). By producing an abundance of stable and chemically diverse SOC compounds, they are significant contributors to SOC sequestration (Kallenbach et al., 2016). With each iterative turnover of the soil microbial biomass, microbial residues are partially metabolized by the remaining soil microbial community, while a fraction of the microbial necromass is stabilized by the soil matrix (Buckeridge et al., 2020). This so-called *in-vivo* turnover (Liang et al., 2017; Sokol et al., 2019) has been identified as an important pathway of C in terrestrial ecosystems. Liang et al. (2019) demonstrated that microbial necromass C contributed to >50 % of SOC in a temperate agricultural soil. Agricultural management techniques such as soil tillage are known to affect soil microbial biomass and community composition (Huang et al., 2013; Kabir, 2005; Mathew et al., 2012), and subsequently their necromass contribution to SOC. However, it is rather unclear how reduced tillage affects the microbial necromass composition in soil.

Within the soil microbial community, soil fungi appear to be important facilitators of long-term SOC storage in soils (Haddaway et al., 2017; Six et al., 2006; Wallander et al., 2013). They can produce a wide range of hydrolytic and oxidative extracellular enzymes to degrade complex organic compounds (Frey, 2019) and thus play an important role in the so-called *ex-vivo* modification of plant materials and residues (Liang et al., 2017). They also tend to use C more efficiently and have a slower biomass turnover as compared to bacteria (Keiblinger et al., 2010; Soares and Rousk, 2019; Strickland and Rousk, 2010). Moreover, their extensive net of fungal hyphae can form more stable soil aggregates where both particulate and mineral-associated organic C are stabilized (Kabir, 2005; Lal, 2013; Totsche et al., 2018). Thus, facilitating the abundance of soil fungi could support the build-up of SOC in the long term (Bailey et al., 2002). A decrease in tillage intensity has in some cases led to a shift in the soil microbial community towards fungal dominance (Bhattarai, 2015; Sanaullah et al., 2020), probably due to reduced disruption of the fungal mycelium. On the other hand, several existing studies do not report a promotion of fungi with decreasing tillage intensity (Helgason et al., 2009; Spedding et al., 2004; Strickland and Rousk, 2010); thus, the body of empirical evidence is far from definitive.

Therefore, this study aims to investigate the inter-relationships between SOC, aggregate stability, and selected microbial biomass and necromass indicators after thirteen years of reduced soil tillage (hereafter 'conservation tillage'). Bulk as well as rhizosphere topsoil samples were taken from four different soil tillage systems, ranging from conventional tillage (high intensity) to no-tillage practices (low intensity). To evaluate SOC dynamics, we examined total SOC pools and dissolved organic C (DOC) responses to conservation tillage. Fungal abundance was analysed through the determination of ergosterol and glomalin-related soil protein (GRSP). Microbial necromass was determined using amino sugar analysis.

Accordingly, we hypothesized that H1) reduced tillage intensity increases soil fungal abundance and microbial necromass, which subsequently promotes SOC sequestration and soil aggregate stability — with the strongest response expected in the no-tillage system; and H2) responses of soil physical and biochemical characteristics to reduced tillage intensity differ between rhizosphere and bulk soil.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study site and experimental setup

The experimental site (0.8 ha) was established in 2006 at the Holabrunn Agricultural College, Lower Austria, Austria (48° 33' N, 16° 03' E; 238 m a.s.l.). Climatic data from 1981 to 2010 recorded 519 mm mean annual precipitation (with the highest precipitation in June) and 9.2 °C mean annual temperature (ZAMG, 2020). The soil is classified as Chernozem (CH) from loess (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015) with silty

loamy texture and 1.39 g cm⁻³ bulk density. The soil contains 0.09 % N and 1–2 % SOC (Weninger et al., 2019). The soil is slightly alkaline, with a soil pH (in MilliQ water) of 7.8 and a carbonate content of 9.9 %. Electrical conductivity (EC) is 127.9 μS cm⁻¹.

Four different tillage intensities have been operated in a stripe-wise block design (6 m × 60 m) with three replicates (see Supplementary Fig. 1). The tillage operations under the different treatments comprised: (i) conventional tillage, i.e. cultivator-ploughing-seedbed preparation-sowing; (ii) reduced tillage, i.e. cultivator-disking-sowing; (iii) minimum tillage, i.e. 5 cm disking-direct sowing; and (iv) no-tillage, i.e. direct sowing. In conventional and reduced tillage treatments, ploughing and cultivator-disking were conducted at a depth of ~25 cm. Fertilization and weed control remained equal among plots and were as follows: application of chemical fertilizer at 132.3 kg N ha⁻¹ (91.8 and 40.5 kg N ha⁻¹ in April and June 2019, respectively), and pre- and post-emergence herbicide sprayings in March and June 2019, respectively. A cover crop mix (soy bean, phacelia, buckwheat, oilseed radish, common vetch, pea) was grown over the winter of 2018/2019. The main crop in 2019 was maize (*Zea mays* L.) sown in April 2019 with a spacing of 75 cm × 18 cm. The average maize yield in 2019 was 12 t ha⁻¹, ranging from 11.7 t ha⁻¹ in conventional tillage to 12.3 t ha⁻¹ in no-tillage. Significant differences in yield were not found among tillage systems (ANOVA and Tukey test, *p* > 0.05).

2.2. Soil sampling

Composite soil samples were collected from the experimental plots in July 2019 at the beginning of the maize flowering stage (BBCH 60). In every plot, three sampling points were placed along a line transect at an interval of 15 m. Bulk soil samples were taken from the sampling points between maize rows using a soil core auger (Ø 7 cm) to a depth of 15 cm. Three soil cores within a 2 m × 2 m area were taken at each sample point to form a composite sample. We obtained rhizosphere soil samples by taking a soil core directly above immediately cut maize plants, containing the top 15 cm of the root system. After soil coring, the bulk soil was carefully shaken off, and the root systems was vigorously shaken in a plastic bag to obtain rhizosphere soil. Samples were immediately placed in a cooling box, transported to the laboratory on the same day, and stored at 4 °C. Prior to analysis, soil samples were sieved to pass 2 mm. Fresh soil was used for the analysis of ergosterol, GRSP, and amino sugars, while other parameters (SOC, total N, DOC, aggregate stability) were analysed on air-dried samples. Overall, a total of 24 samples (4 tillage intensities × 2 soil zones × 3 replicates) were used for soil physical and biochemical analyses.

2.3. Soil physical analyses

Determination of soil aggregate stability was done by the sieve immersion procedure following the Austrian standard ÖNORM L1072 (Austrian Standards, 2004) with analytical triplicates. The results are expressed as percent.

Bulk density was measured from undisturbed soil samples taken with stainless steel sample rings with a volume of 250 cm³ after drying at 105 °C for 24 h and weighing. Subsequently, stocks for nutrients, fungal biomass indicators, and amino sugars were calculated as mg, g or kg m⁻² of the first 15 cm of topsoil.

2.4. Soil biochemical analyses

Soil carbonate content was analysed with a Scheibler device as described in ÖNORM L1084 (Austrian Standards, 1989). Total C and N were measured by dry combustion method with a CHNS/O elemental analyser (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., USA). The concentration of SOC was obtained by the subtraction of the inorganic C content from total C and is expressed in kg m⁻². A probe sonicator (SONOPLUS HD2200, BANDELIN electronic GmbH & Co., Berlin, Germany) was applied to

extract DOC from a soil-water suspension (10 g soil in 100 ml MilliQ water) with 1 cm insert depth at 2 μm amplitude for 2 min as adapted from Schomakers et al. (2014). After filtration through 0.45 μm double filters (a folded filter and a nylon membrane filter), filtrates were measured for DOC with a UV-Vis diode array spectrophotometer (Agilent 8453, Agilent Technologies Inc., USA) using a 1 cm quartz cuvette. DOC was measured via UV-absorbance at the 254 nm wavelength and converted to DOC concentration according to Brandstetter et al. (1996). DOC contents are expressed in g m^{-2} .

Ergosterol was extracted following Gong et al. (2001) and Sae-Tun et al. (2020) with minor modifications. Briefly, 3 g soil with 30 ml methanol (MeOH) was shaken overnight on an overhead shaker. After centrifugation and filtration using a 0.45 μm folded filter, ergosterol concentrations were measured from the filtrates using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC; Agilent 1100 series HPLC, Agilent Technologies Inc., USA). Separation was conducted on a C18 reverse phase column connected to a UV detector set at 282 nm and using a mixture of 95 % MeOH and 5 % MilliQ water as the mobile phase with a retention time of ca. 6 min 50 s. External standards ranging from 0.78 to 25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ were prepared in MeOH. Ergosterol concentrations are expressed in g m^{-2} .

Glomalin-related soil protein (GRSP) was extracted from 1 g of soil as an upscaling of Wright and Upadhyaya (1998). The concentration of easily extractable (EEG) and total glomalin (TG) were quantified from the supernatants immediately according to a Bradford assay (Bradford, 1976) with 10–100 mg l^{-1} Bovine serum albumin (BSA) as external standards. The measurement was carried out on a spectrophotometric plate reader Enspire Multimode 2300 (Perkin Elmer Inc., USA). GRSP was obtained from the sum of EEG and TG concentrations. GRSP contents are expressed in g m^{-2} . However, we wish to draw attention to the potential interference of co-extracted compounds such as protein from non-arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi origin, lipids and humic materials with GRSP extraction and quantification method used (Irving et al., 2021).

For the extraction of amino sugars, we followed the method described by Appuhn et al. (2004). Briefly, 0.5 g soil was extracted in 10 ml of a 6 M HCl boiling for 6 h. After filtration, a 1 ml aliquot was evaporated at 55 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under nitrogen atmosphere to dryness. Then, the sample was rinsed with 1 ml water and re-evaporated. The sample was filled up with 1 ml 0.04 M $\text{Na}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ buffer and centrifuged at 5000 g for 10 min. The supernatant was passed through 0.45 μm PTFE membrane filter and stored at -18°C prior to HPLC measurement. Quantification of amino sugars with HPLC and fluorescence spectroscopy was modified from Appuhn et al. (2004) and Indorf et al. (2011). For the pre-column derivatisation, 2 μl extracted solution, 20 μl ortho-phthalaldehyde (OPA) reagent (Agilent 5061-3335), and 5 μl 0.4 N borate buffer, pH 10.2 (Agilent 5061-3339) were mixed by an autosampler (Agilent G4226A, Agilent Technologies Inc., USA). After 2 min of reaction time, 0.5 μl indole derivatives were injected into the HPLC system (Agilent 1290 Infinity series, Agilent Technologies Inc., USA) equipped with C18 reverse phase column (Zorbax Eclipse Plus C18 RR, 4.6 mm \times 100 mm). The separation was performed at 50 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a flow rate of 1.5 ml min^{-1} using a gradient mixture of two eluents as a mobile phase. Eluent A was a mixture of 0.05 M sodium citrate, 4 mM sodium acetate (pH 5.3), MeOH, and tetrahydrofuran in a ratio of 90:8.5:0.75:0.75 (v:v:v:v). Eluent B was a mixture of MilliQ water and MeOH (50:50, v:v). Total duration for each run was 21 min with the eluent gradient starting with eluent A for 2 min, followed by A:B at 80:20 (v:v) for 16 min and remain isocratic for 1 min, eluent B for 1 min, and eluent A last for 1 min, respectively. External standards of D-mannosamine hydrochloride, muramic acid, D-(+)-galactosamine hydrochloride, and D-(+)-glucosamine hydrochloride were prepared in MilliQ water at concentrations of up to 10 mg l^{-1} . Amino sugar contents are expressed in g m^{-2} .

2.5. Statistical analysis

We evaluated soil physical and biochemical differences between tillage intensities (i.e., conventional, reduced, minimum and no-tillage) and soil zones (i.e., bulk and rhizosphere soil) within each tillage intensity using multivariate analysis of variances (MANOVA). Using a type III sum of square model, we tested whether tillage intensity and soil zone (rhizosphere vs. bulk) as main effects significantly affected our analysed parameters. The model included 'block' as an additional fixed factor. As block had no significant effect in the overall model ($\lambda = 0.037$, $F = 1.526$; $p = 0.276$) and its effect was not a study focus, results on block effects are thus not presented further on. Soil zone was used as a (spatially) repeated factor following the approach of Beuschel et al. (2019) and Piepho et al. (2004). Moreover, we tested for interaction effects between tillage intensity and soil zone. To evaluate the statistical significance of the overall model, we used the Wilks' lambda distributions (λ) and derived F- and p-values for the main and the interaction effects. Post-hoc Tukey tests within the MANOVA analysis were used to evaluate significant differences among tillage systems. Linear relationships between the measured physical and biochemical variables were evaluated using repeated (for bulk and rhizosphere soil) measures correlation coefficients (r_{rm}). The analysis was conducted in R using the package 'rmcorr' (Bakdash and Marusich, 2017).

In order to assess the causal relationships between soil physical and biochemical parameters, partial least square structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) was applied following the approach of Haenlein and Kaplan (2004). Contrary to other SEM approaches, PLS-SEM is an exploratory rather than a confirmatory modelling approach and can process rather small sample sizes with low sensitivity to data distribution (Chin and Newsted, 1999; Fan et al., 2016; Hair et al., 2014, 2019; Ravand and Purya, 2016). Following the current state of knowledge on tillage-induced changes of soil organic matter dynamics (cf. Introduction), we constructed an initial hypothesized model that total SOC stocks and soil aggregate stability in agricultural soil are essentially driven by labile organic carbon fraction, particularly those related to soil microbiology. Specifically, we hypothesized a strong effect of fungal abundance (as indicated by ergosterol and GRSP content), via microbial necromass, on SOC and aggregate stability. Accordingly, ergosterol and GRSP were combined in the latent variable 'living fungi', while the four measured amino sugars were subsumed under the latent variable 'microbial necromass'. We desisted from assessing the relationship for each individual tillage system due to the already small sample size. All observations from both bulk and rhizosphere soils were incorporated in modelling to improve statistical power and to comprehend the causal relationship over field variability. Three outliers were removed from the dataset according to multivariate outlier identification by the Mahalanobis distance to minimize statistical errors and bias prior to PLS-SEM analysis (Korkmaz et al., 2014; Senthamarai Kannan and Manoj, 2015). All measurement models were constructed in a reflective manner due to strong correlations among measured variables (Haenlein and Kaplan, 2004; Hair et al., 2019). All possible models derived from our initial hypothesized model were evaluated following the procedure of Sarstedt et al. (2017) to obtain the best fitting result. As a result of our *a priori* model fitting approach, total N and the soil C:N ratio were excluded from the presented model. Evaluation of the fitted models' reliability was assessed and systematically compared following the fit indices and bootstrapped confidence intervals (Haenlein and Kaplan, 2004; Hair et al., 2019; Sarstedt et al., 2017). The selected models were acceptable when (i) the measurement models performed outer loadings (loadings of measured variables on their responsive latent variables) > 0.7 ; (ii) the internal consistency reliability, as indicated by Dillon-Goldstein's rho, ranged from 0.60 to ≤ 0.95 ; (iii) the average variance extract (AVE), an indicator of convergent validity, was ≥ 0.5 ; (iv) the presented discriminant validity of the measured variables was greater, with the given latent variable, than with other latent variables; and (v) the structural model (path model) exhibited a coefficient of

determination (R^2) > 0.5, a predictive accuracy (Q^2) > 0.5, and non-collinearity indicated by the variance inflation factor (VIF) < 10. Significance of path coefficients and outer loadings were determined at 95 % bootstrap confidence intervals.

We refer to significant effects, differences, and relationships at $p < 0.05$. Statistical analyses were conducted in SPSS 26 and R software 3.6.3. In particular, the PLS-SEM was conducted using the R package 'semPLS' (Monecke and Leisch, 2012).

3. Results

3.1. Tillage intensity effects on soil physical and biochemical parameters

Overall, the MANOVA revealed a significant effect of tillage intensity on our tested soil physical and biochemical parameters (Wilks' $\lambda = 0.003$, $F_{12,49,33} = 2.458$, $p = 0.046$). Test statistics on the individual parameters can be found in Table 1.

SOC stocks were significantly higher under minimum and no-tillage compared to conventional tillage ($p < 0.01$; Table 1, Fig. 1a). Soils under minimum and no-tillage contained 40 and 39 % more SOC, respectively, than soils under conventional tillage. Total N stocks were significantly increased in all conservation tillage systems, with the highest contents under minimum tillage (Fig. 1b). As total N increases were relatively higher than SOC increases under reduced tillage intensities, the soil C:N ratio significantly decreased in conservation tillage systems as compared to the conventional tillage system (Fig. 1c). DOC stocks increased significantly with the reduction of tillage intensity, and the highest contents were found under minimum tillage (Fig. 1d). Soil aggregate stability increased significantly in the minimum and no-tillage systems (Fig. 1e); from ~20 % under conventional tillage to ~40 % under minimum and no-tillage.

Ergosterol contents showed a strong and significant response to conservation tillage (Fig. 2a), with the highest contents under minimum tillage. Ergosterol contents increased by 280, 349 and 177 % under reduced, minimum and no-tillage, respectively, as compared to conventional tillage. GRSP was also significantly increased by ~35 % under

Table 1

Test statistics of the MANOVA analysis to evaluate the effect of soil tillage intensity (Tillage), soil zone and the interaction of those two parameters on individual soil physical and biochemical parameters (SOC, soil organic C; DOC, dissolved organic C; GRSP, glomalin-related soil protein). Given are Wilks' λ , degrees of freedom (Df), and F- and p-values for the overall model, and F- and p-values for individual parameters.

Overall model					
	Tillage		Soil zone		Tillage \times Soil zone
Wilks' λ	0.003		0.211		0.035
Df	12.49,33		4,11		12.49,33
F-value	2.458		1.359		0.799
p-Value	0.046		0.413		0.709

Individual parameters						
	Tillage		Soil zone		Tillage \times Soil zone	
	F	p	F	p	F	p
SOC	10.16	<0.001	3.03	0.104	1.15	0.365
Total N	13.70	<0.001	0.03	0.876	0.81	0.512
C:N ratio	10.03	<0.001	0.70	0.418	1.32	0.308
DOC	48.20	<0.001	4.61	0.050	2.58	0.095
Soil aggregate stability	67.76	<0.001	0.56	0.467	1.15	0.362
Ergosterol	14.78	<0.001	0.05	0.823	0.69	0.575
GRSP	11.38	<0.001	0.08	0.785	0.58	0.641
Mannosamine	1.15	0.257	1.95	0.185	0.52	0.674
Muramic acid	31.06	<0.001	0.03	0.876	2.40	0.112
Galactosamine	10.91	<0.001	0.66	0.429	2.28	0.125
Glucosamine	13.97	<0.001	0.06	0.807	3.29	0.052

both minimum and no-tillage (Fig. 2b).

In general, glucosamine had the highest contribution (42 %) to total amino sugar concentrations, followed by muramic acid (38 %), galactosamine (16 %) and mannosamine (3 %) (see Supplementary Fig. 2). The amino sugars muramic acid, galactosamine and glucosamine – yet not mannosamine – were affected by reduced tillage intensity, exhibiting significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) and similar contents in all conservation tillage systems (Fig. 3a–d). The relative contribution of amino sugars did not shift with conservation tillage systems (data not shown).

3.2. Effects of bulk vs. rhizosphere on soil physical and biochemical parameters

Soil zone had significant effect neither on the overall model (Wilks' $\lambda = 0.211$, $F_{4,11} = 1.359$, $p = 0.413$) nor on each individual parameter (Table 1). We also detected no significant effect from the interaction between tillage intensity and soil zone (Wilks' $\lambda = 0.035$, $F_{12,49,33} = 0.799$, $p = 0.709$). However, marginally significant effect of soil zone was observed for DOC, with 6.5 % higher contents recorded in rhizosphere soil ($p = 0.05$, Table 1).

3.3. Relationships among soil physical and biochemical parameters

Across all tillage systems, we detected strong correlations between soil physical and biochemical parameters (Fig. 4). SOC and DOC were strongly linked to fungal biomass indicators, microbial necromass as indicated by amino sugar concentrations, and aggregate stability. Among the amino sugars, muramic acid was particularly well correlated to SOC and its dissolved fraction, aggregate stability and ergosterol contents. On the other hand, mannosamine showed the weakest correlative relations to the other soil parameters.

We applied PLS-SEM to better understand how SOC and aggregate stability are related to DOC, fungal abundance and microbial necromass (Fig. 5). The model showed reliable indicators' loadings (all loadings >0.7), good internal consistency reliability (Dillon-Goldstein's rho ranging between 0.90 and 0.94), very good convergence (AVE = 0.81), and satisfactory discriminant validity. Furthermore, the model had a high predictive accuracy with Q^2 between 0.54 and 0.75. VIF of all variables, except of DOC, was <10. The obtained R^2 values indicated that the model could well explain the variation in SOC ($R^2 = 0.81$) and aggregate stability ($R^2 = 0.64$), and living soil fungi and microbial necromass were found to be strong predictors ($R^2 = 0.72$ and 0.70, respectively).

DOC exerted a strong positive direct effect on living soil fungi (i.e., ergosterol and GRSP; direct effect = 0.85) and subsequently had an indirect and moderate impact on microbial necromass, soil aggregate stability and SOC; with indirect effect sizes of 0.71, 0.68 and 0.65, respectively. Living soil fungi strongly influenced microbial necromass (direct effect = 0.83) and soil aggregate stability (direct effect = 0.80), yet no direct relationship to SOC was detected. On the other hand, a strong positive relationship between microbial necromass and SOC was found (direct effect = 0.61). Further details on the SEM can be found in Supplementary Table 1.

4. Discussion

We detected strong effects of tillage intensity reduction on soil physical and biochemical parameters (Fig. 1–3). It is well established that conventional tillage measures such as ploughing can degrade soil structure as compared to conservation tillage practices (Pagliai et al., 2004). This might consequently affect crop production through reduced water retention, diminished root growth and decreased nutrient availability (Pires et al., 2017; Pirmoradian et al., 2005; Rasmussen, 1999; Tagar et al., 2020). Accordingly, thirteen years of conservation tillage had a strong positive effect on soil aggregate stability (Fig. 1e). The response was particularly pronounced in the minimum and the no-

Fig. 1. (a) Soil organic C (SOC), (b) total N, (c) the C:N ratio, (d) dissolved organic C (DOC) and (e) soil aggregate stability in bulk and rhizosphere topsoil (0–15 cm) under different tillage intensities. Presented bar is the mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). Different letters indicate significant differences among tillage intensities, as determined by MANOVA followed by post-hoc Tukey tests ($p < 0.05$).

tillage systems, where aggregate stability increased by more than two-fold compared to the conventional tillage system. These results are in line with our first hypothesis and results from previous studies (Bartlová et al., 2015; Beuschel et al., 2019; Six et al., 2000).

In accordance with these results, our PLS-SEM evidenced strong relationships between living fungal biomass indicators (ergosterol and GRSP) and soil aggregate stability (Fig. 5). This is also supported by numerous other studies (Bearden and Petersen, 2000; Bossuyt et al., 2001; Duchicela et al., 2013; Molope et al., 1987; Rezáčová et al., 2021; Yang et al., 2017). Fungi are able to stabilize the soil matrix (i) biophysically through the enmeshment of soil particles with their extensive extramatrical mycelium and the physical alignment of organic matter and clay particles, leading to the formation of microaggregates; (ii) biochemically through the production and secretion of substances such as GRSP, mucilages, polysaccharides and other extracellular compounds, which act as strong particle-binding agents; and (iii) biologically through their beneficial effect on soil microbial communities and the soil food web (Agnihotri et al., 2021; Bronick and Lal, 2005; Rillig and Mummey, 2006; Six et al., 2004; Yang et al., 2017). We therefore conclude that greater soil aggregate stability under conservation tillage is, among other factors, a consequence of increased fungal biomass.

Within the fungal biomass indicators, ergosterol showed a strong response to tillage intensity reduction (Fig. 2). Ergosterol concentrations increased by approximately five-fold under reduced and minimum

tillage, and three-fold under no-tillage compared with conventional tillage. We further detected nearly 30 % increases in GRSP, a proxy for arbuscular mycorrhizal fungal abundance, under conservation tillage systems (Fig. 2b). Significant soil physical disturbances caused by tillage can create unfavourable conditions for soil fungi. The fungal mycelium can be damaged during the tillage process (Helgason et al., 2009; Hendrix et al., 1986), subsequently reducing fungal abundance in intensively tilled soils (Hydbom et al., 2017; Strickland and Rousk, 2010). Contrarily, better access to substrates and nutrients particularly in the topsoil as well as more favourable microclimatic conditions through conservation tillage practices can additionally benefit soil fungal growth (Kladivko, 2001; Peixoto et al., 2020).

A strong relationship between DOC and fungal biomass (Fig. 5) suggests that increased DOC contents under conservation tillage facilitated the growth of soil fungi in those soil systems. It further implied a strong control of microbial C assimilation by substrate quality (Cotrufu et al., 2013; Xu et al., 2014). DOC is an easily available C substrate and plays a significant role in soil C cycling, as plants channel up to 60 % of photosynthetically-derived C to the root system, including tissues, mucilage, or the exudation of organic compounds (Clemmensen et al., 2013; Högberg et al., 2001). It can be metabolized by soil bacteria and fungi and results in the formation of more complex C compounds with lower degradability (Ali et al., 2020; Sokol et al., 2019; Sokol and Bradford, 2019). Therefore, conservation tillage promotes the growth of

Fig. 2. Contents of (a) ergosterol and (b) glomalin-related soil protein (GRSP) in bulk and rhizosphere topsoil (0–15 cm) under different tillage intensities. Presented bar is the mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). Different letters indicate significant differences between tillage intensities, as determined by MANOVA followed by post-hoc Tukey tests ($p < 0.05$).

fungal mycelia, which in turn affect soil aggregate stabilization and SOC storage (Kabir, 2005; Strickland and Rousk, 2010; van Groenigen et al., 2010). This notion has been confirmed by a recent meta-analysis that could show a strong positive effect of conservation tillage practices on soil fungal biomass (Chen et al., 2020).

Soil aggregation has been suggested to be one of the major processes governing SOC sequestration (Abrar et al., 2020; Six et al., 2004), as organic residues either from plants or soil microorganisms get physically sheltered in micro- and macro-aggregates and thus protected from microbial mineralization (Blanco-Canqui and Lal, 2004). A strong mechanical disintegration of soil aggregates, particularly in conventional tillage systems with high energy input and the subsequent release of CO₂, can enhance SOC mineralization and thus negatively affect SOC

Fig. 4. Heat map showing the relationships among soil physical and biochemical parameters across all tillage intensities using a repeated-measures correlation ($n = 24$). The repeated measure correlation coefficient (r_{rm}) is given, and significant correlations at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.001$ are indicated by *, ** and ***, respectively.

Fig. 3. Contents of (a) mannosamine, (b) muramic acid, (c) galactosamine and (d) glucosamine in bulk and rhizosphere topsoil (0–15 cm) under different tillage intensities. Presented bar is the mean \pm SD ($n = 3$). Different letters indicate significant differences between tillage intensities, as determined by MANOVA followed by post-hoc Tukey tests ($p < 0.05$) (n.s., not significant).

Fig. 5. Final structural equation model showing influential pathways of biochemical parameters (DOC, dissolved organic C; GRSP, glomalin-related soil protein) on soil aggregate stability (SAS) and soil organic C (SOC). Bold numbers below parameters display R^2 values. Arrows with numbers between latent variables (ellipses) present direct paths and the standardized path coefficients, and arrows with numbers between the latent variables and the measured variables (rectangles) present loadings. Black and grey colours indicate significant ($p < 0.05$) and non-significant ($p \geq 0.05$) coefficients, respectively.

sequestration (Chenu et al., 2019; Six et al., 2000). Thus, it was surprising not to find a significant causal relationship between aggregate stability and SOC (Fig. 5). This suggests that total SOC is not necessarily a strong predictor for aggregate stability and emphasizes that other functional carbon pools such as microbial C and DOC are likely more relevant and strongly related to aggregate-associated C, which was recently demonstrated by Shen et al. (2021).

Indeed, thirteen years of conservation tillage increased SOC stocks by 40 and 39 % under minimum and no-tillage compared with conventional tillage, respectively (Fig. 1a). This further supports our first hypothesis and agrees with the results from other studies, which reported changes of similar magnitude (Ogle et al., 2005). Thus, tillage intensity reduction poses a great potential for increasing SOC sequestration in agricultural soils. It remains to be evaluated when such reduced tillage systems reach a steady state of SOC accumulation (Alvarez, 2005). In this regard, other factors such as climatic conditions, irrigation, organic amendments, increasing belowground inputs and nutrient (particularly N) management are important to consider to fully utilize the C sequestration potential of agricultural soils (Chenu et al., 2019; Dimassi et al., 2014; Paustian et al., 2016).

We further hypothesized that SOC stocks would show the strongest increase under no-tillage. This however was not the case, as SOC contents were comparable to minimum tillage (Fig. 1a). Soils under no-tillage can be vulnerable to soil compaction (Blanco-Canqui and Ruis, 2018; Peixoto et al., 2020; Reichert et al., 2009). Together with the decreased rearrangement of soil particles (Peixoto et al., 2020) and the reduced exposure of organic residues and compounds to soil microbes (Sanaullah et al., 2020), plant as well as microbial growth could be impeded and this would subsequently diminish the build-up of SOC in a no-tillage system.

A strong positive relationship between microbial necromass and SOC – as evident from the PLS-SEM (Fig. 5) – emphasizes a major role of microbial necromass in SOC sequestration in terrestrial ecosystems (Kallenbach et al., 2016; Liang et al., 2017; Liang and Balsler, 2011). Amino sugars have been proposed as a proxy for microbial necromass (Amelung, 2001; Guggenberger et al., 1999). As certain amino sugars are derived from specific phylogenetic groups of soil microorganisms, they can be used as indicators for the origin of microbial necromass. For example, muramic acid and galactosamine are almost exclusively produced by bacteria, while glucosamine is mostly of fungal origin (Guggenberger et al., 1999; Joergensen, 2018; Parsons, 1981). This was also

supported by significantly strong correlation ($p < 0.05$, $r_{\text{mm}} = 0.69$) between glucosamine and ergosterol contents (Fig. 4). Overall, we found a strong contribution of muramic acid and glucosamine to total amino sugar concentrations in our tillage systems, representing ~38 and 42 %, respectively (Supplementary Fig. 2). This suggests that both bacterial and fungal residues contribute to the soil microbial necromass pool. Muramic acid, galactosamine, and glucosamine significantly increased in all conservation tillage systems (Fig. 3). These results are in accordance with existing literature showing that conservation tillage strategies increase the abundance of amino sugars (Ding et al., 2011; Li et al., 2019). We did not find any significant shifts between bacterial- to fungal-derived amino sugars, suggesting that conservation tillage exhibits advantageous conditions for both fungal and bacterial biomass and subsequently necromass (Hydbom et al., 2017; Strickland and Rousk, 2010). Although we would have expected a stronger contribution of fungal-derived amino sugars with decreasing tillage intensity, as indicated by increased ergosterol concentrations, the slightly alkaline soil (pH 7.8) and regular application of fertilizer represents conditions that should benefit bacteria over fungi (Rousk et al., 2010); thus, the positive effects might have counteracted each other. Moreover, relative abundances of bacterial and fungal biomass in soil do not necessarily imply similar relative abundances of bacterial and fungal necromass (Joergensen, 2018; Li et al., 2015). For example, Li et al. (2015) showed that fungal-derived necromass was dominant in a bacterial dominated soil microbial community probably due to better stabilization and protection of fungal-derived necromass and a faster turnover of bacterial-derived necromass.

Our PLS-SEM further detected a strong link between fungal biomass and microbial necromass indicators (Fig. 5). Subsequently, microbial necromass was strongly positively associated with SOC stocks. These relationships give rise to a strong microbial control of SOC accumulation in agricultural soils (Kallenbach et al., 2015; Liang et al., 2017, 2019; Six et al., 2006). Liang et al. (2017) proposed two main mechanisms by which soil microbes drive SOC storage: *ex-vivo* transformation, i.e. the transformation of plant residues into stable SOC forms apart from microbial assimilation; and *in-vivo* turnover, i.e. SOC build-up through microbial-derived C as a consequence of microbial anabolic and metabolic activities. As the soil microbial biomass turns over, a fraction of the derived microbial residues is being stabilized by the soil matrix (Buckeridge et al., 2020) by occlusion in soil aggregates and associations with soil minerals (Liang, 2020; Sokol et al., 2019; Sokol and Bradford, 2019). We therefore suggest that *in-vivo* turnover is a prominent mechanism driving SOC accumulation in our tested agricultural soils across all tillage intensities, and that soil fungi play a major role in SOC storage (Bailey et al., 2002; Veloso et al., 2020).

The rhizosphere is known to be a microbial and biochemical hotspot in soil (Kuzaykov and Blagodatskaya, 2015; Pathan et al., 2020). The distinct rhizosphere environment selects for a specific microbial community and is often characterized by increased nutrient turnover (Essel et al., 2019; Kumar et al., 2013; Larsen et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2017). We have therefore hypothesized that bulk and rhizosphere soil would differ in physical and biochemical characteristics as well as in their response to conservation tillage. We were surprised to observe no significant differences between the two soil zones, and their response to different tillage intensities was rather equal (Table 1). Only DOC contents were overall marginally ($p = 0.05$) higher in the rhizosphere soil. This might be related to an additional input of simple C-rich compounds from rhizodeposition (Angst et al., 2018; Kuzaykov and Blagodatskaya, 2015).

Although our study presents a comprehensive picture on the biochemical responses and mechanisms that facilitate increased SOC sequestration and soil aggregate stability under various soil tillage systems, there are potential shortcomings that need to be stressed. In particular, the small sample size and the uni-directional characteristic of our PLS-SEM approach might restrict statistical power and interpretation of the model. For example, Buckeridge et al. (2020) recently

demonstrated that microbial necromass not only facilitates SOC sequestration but also constitutes a C input variable. This feedback could not be captured within our SEM approach due to the limit of the explanatory power of PLS-SEM. Deeper mechanistic insights into these feedback relations in the frame of the *in-vivo* pathway (Liang et al., 2017) would require targeted measurements (e.g. via isotope labelling) that are currently still not available from long-term tillage field experiments (Buckeridge et al., 2020; Liang, 2020). Moreover, edaphic properties such as soil texture and environmental conditions might shape biochemical responses to tillage intensity reduction; this highlights the need for further studies using different soil types and under varying environmental conditions to verify and strengthen our findings.

5. Conclusions

Thirteen years of conservation tillage significantly increased soil aggregate stability, soil C and N pools, fungal biomass and microbial necromass contents, with responses being particularly pronounced under minimum and no-tillage. Overall, differences of the responses between bulk and rhizosphere soil were minor. We suggest that increased C availability under conservation tillage systems, as indicated by greater DOC contents, facilitated fungal growth. These observed increases in fungal biomass directly affected soil aggregate stability through biochemical and physical stabilization, and promoted the formation of microbial necromass. The strong link between microbial necromass and SOC suggests that the build-up of SOC under conservation tillage is mediated by increased microbial C assimilation and the subsequent accelerated turnover of microbial biomass to necromass. Therefore, we suggest that conservation tillage is a valuable tool to increase SOC sequestration via the promotion of soil microbial activity and the improvement of the aggregate stability in agricultural soils.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

The authors received financial support from the Horizon 2020 European Joint Programme SOIL (EJP-SOIL) [grant number 862695]. Orracha Sae-Tun is the recipient of the Ernst Mach Grant ASEA-UNET from Austria's Agency for Education and Internationalisation (OeAD). We are grateful to Andre Wittmann and Maximilian Breiner for their support during soil sampling and laboratory analyses and Elisabeth Kopecky, Astrid Hobel and Karin Hackl for their support during the laboratory work. We thank Dr. Josef Rosner, DI Harald Summerer and Franz Ecker, who have planned and managed the long-term tillage trial at the Agricultural College (LFS) Hollabrunn since its very beginning, for their cooperation to carry out this study. We also acknowledge Joanne O'Keefe for language editing.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2022.104599>.

References

Abrar, M.M., Xu, M., Shah, S.A.A., Aslam, M.W., Aziz, T., Mustafa, A., Ashraf, M.N., Zhou, B., Ma, X., 2020. Variations in the profile distribution and protection mechanisms of organic carbon under long-term fertilization in a Chinese Mollisol. *Sci. Total Environ.* 723, 138181 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138181>.
Agnihotri, R., Bharti, A., Ramesh, A., Prakash, A., Sharma, M.P., 2021. Glomalin related protein and C16:1ω5 PLFA associated with AM fungi as potential signatures for

assessing the soil C sequestration under contrasting soil management practices. *Eur. J. Soil Biol.* 103, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejsobi.2021.103286>.
Ali, R.S., Poll, C., Kandeler, E., 2020. Soil properties control microbial carbon assimilation and its mean residence time. *Front. Environ. Sci.* 8, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2020.00033>.
Alvarez, R., 2005. A review of nitrogen fertilizer and conservation tillage effects on soil organic carbon storage. *Soil Use Manag.* 21, 38–52. <https://doi.org/10.1079/sum2005291>.
Amelung, W., 2001. Methods using amino sugars as markers for microbial residues in soil. In: Kimble, J.M., Stewart, B.A., Follett, R.F. (Eds.), *Assessment Methods for Soil Carbon*. Lewis Publishers, Boca Raton, pp. 233–272. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781482278644-27>.
Angst, G., Messinger, J., Greiner, M., Häusler, W., Hertel, D., Kirfel, K., Kögel-Knabner, I., Leuschner, C., Rethemeyer, J., Mueller, C.W., 2018. Soil organic carbon stocks in topsoil and subsoil controlled by parent material, carbon input in the rhizosphere, and microbial-derived compounds. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 122, 19–30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2018.03.026>.
Appuhn, A., Joergensen, R.G., Raubuch, M., Scheller, E., Wilke, B., 2004. The automated determination of glucosamine, galactosamine, muramic acid, and mannosamine in soil and root hydrolysates by HPLC. *J. Plant Nutr. Soil Sci.* 167, 17–21. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jpln.200321302>.
Austrian Standards, 2004. ÖNORM L 1072, *Physikalische Bodenuntersuchung – Bestimmung der Aggregatstabilität nach dem Siebtauchverfahren*.
Austrian Standards, 1989. ÖNORM L 1084, *Chemische Bodenuntersuchung für die Bestimmung von Carbonat*.
Bailey, V.L., Smith, J.L., Bolton, H., 2002. Fungal-to-bacterial ratios in soils investigated for enhanced C sequestration. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 34, 997–1007. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717\(02\)00033-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717(02)00033-0).
Bakdash, J.Z., Marusich, L.R., 2017. Repeated measures correlation. *Front. Psychol.* 8, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00456>.
Bartlová, J., Badalíková, B., Pospíšilová, L., Pokorný, E., Šarapatka, B., 2015. Water stability of soil aggregates in different systems of Tillage. *Soil Water Res.* 10, 147–154. <https://doi.org/10.17221/132/2014-SWR>.
Bearden, B.N., Petersen, L., 2000. Influence of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi on soil structure and aggregate stability of a vertisol. *Plant Soil* 218, 173–183. <https://doi.org/10.1023/a:1014923911324>.
Beuschel, R., Piepho, H.P., Joergensen, R.G., Wachendorf, C., 2019. Similar spatial patterns of soil quality indicators in three poplar-based silvo-arable alley cropping systems in Germany. *Biol. Fertil. Soils* 55, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-018-1324-3>.
Bhattarai, B., 2015. Variation of soil microbial population in different soil horizons. *J. Microbiol. Exp.* 2 <https://doi.org/10.15406/jmen.2015.02.00044>.
Blanco-Canqui, H., Lal, R., 2004. Mechanisms of carbon sequestration in soil aggregates. *CRC Crit. Rev. Plant Sci.* 23, 481–504. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07352680490886842>.
Blanco-Canqui, H., Ruis, S.J., 2018. No-tillage and soil physical environment. *Geoderma* 326, 164–200. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2018.03.011>.
Bossuyt, H., Denef, K., Six, J., Frey, S.D., Merckx, R., Paustian, K., 2001. Influence of microbial populations and residue quality on aggregate stability. *Appl. Soil Ecol.* 16, 195–208. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0929-1393\(00\)00116-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0929-1393(00)00116-5).
Bradford, M.M., 1976. A rapid and sensitive method for the quantitation of microgram quantities of protein utilizing the principle of protein-dye binding. *Anal. Biochem.* 72, 248–254. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-2697\(76\)90527-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0003-2697(76)90527-3).
Brandstetter, A., Sletten, R.S., Mentler, A., Wenzel, W.W., 1996. Estimating dissolved organic carbon in natural waters by UV absorbance (254 nm). *J. Plant Nutr. Soil Sci.* 159, 605–607. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jpln.1996.3581590612>.
Bronick, C.J., Lal, R., 2005. Soil structure and management: a review. *Geoderma* 124, 3–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2004.03.005>.
Buckeridge, K.M., Mason, K.E., McNamara, N.P., Ostle, N., Puissant, J., Goodall, T., Griffiths, R.I., Stott, A.W., Whitaker, J., 2020. Environmental and microbial controls on microbial necromass recycling, an important precursor for soil carbon stabilization. *Commun. Earth Environ.* 1, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-020-00031-4>.
Chen, H., Dai, Z., Veach, A.M., Zheng, J., Xu, J., Schadt, C.W., 2020. Global meta-analyses show that conservation tillage practices promote soil fungal and bacterial biomass. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 293, 106841 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2020.106841>.
Chenu, C., Angers, D.A., Barré, P., Derrien, D., Arrouays, D., Balesdent, J., 2019. Increasing organic stocks in agricultural soils: knowledge gaps and potential innovations. *Soil Tillage Res.* 188, 41–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2018.04.011>.
Chin, W.W., Newsted, P.R., 1999. Structural equation modeling analysis with small samples using partial least squares. In: Hoyle, R.H. (Ed.), *Statistical Strategies for Small Sample Research*. SAGE Publications Inc, pp. 307–341.
Clemmensen, K.E., Bahr, A., Ovaskainen, O., Dahlberg, A., Ekblad, A., Wallander, H., Stenlid, J., Finlay, R.D., Wardle, D.A., Lindahl, B.D., 2013. Roots and associated fungi drive long-term carbon sequestration in boreal forest. *Science* (80-) 339, 1615–1618. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1231923>.
Cotrufo, M.F., Wallenstein, M.D., Boot, C.M., Denef, K., Paul, E., 2013. The Microbial Efficiency-Matrix Stabilization (MEMS) framework integrates plant litter decomposition with soil organic matter stabilization: do labile plant inputs form stable soil organic matter? *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 19, 988–995. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12113>.
Dimassi, B., Mary, B., Wylleman, R., Labreuche, J.O., Couture, D., Piraux, F., Cohan, J.P., 2014. Long-term effect of contrasted tillage and crop management on soil carbon

- dynamics during 41 years. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 188, 134–146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2014.02.014>.
- Ding, X., Zhang, B., Zhang, Xudong, Yang, X., Zhang, Xiaoping, 2011. Effects of tillage and crop rotation on soil microbial residues in a rainfed agroecosystem of northeast China. *Soil Tillage Res.* 114, 43–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2011.03.008>.
- Duchicela, J., Sullivan, T.S., Bonatti, E., Bever, J.D., 2013. Soil aggregate stability increase is strongly related to fungal community succession along an abandoned agricultural field chronosequence in the Bolivian Altiplano. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 50, 1266–1273. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.12130>.
- Essel, E., Xie, Junhong, Deng, C., Peng, Z., Wang, J., Shen, J., Xie, Jianhui, Coulter, J.A., Li, L., 2019. Bacterial and fungal diversity in rhizosphere and bulk soil under different long-term tillage and cereal/legume rotation. *Soil Tillage Res.* 194 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2019.104302>.
- Fan, Y., Chen, J., Shirkey, G., John, R., Wu, S.R., Park, H., Shao, C., 2016. Applications of structural equation modeling (SEM) in ecological studies: an updated review. *Ecol. Process.* 5, 5–19. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13717-016-0063-3>.
- Frey, S.D., 2019. Mycorrhizal fungi as mediators of soil organic matter dynamics. *Annu. Rev. Ecol. Evol. Syst.* 50, 237–259. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-ecolsys-110617-062331>.
- Gong, P., Guan, X., Witter, E., 2001. A rapid method to extract ergosterol from soil by physical disruption. *Appl. Soil Ecol.* 17, 285–289. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0929-1393\(01\)00141-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0929-1393(01)00141-X).
- Guggenberger, G., Frey, S.D., Six, J., Paustian, K., Elliott, E.T., 1999. Bacterial and fungal cell-wall residues in conventional and no-tillage agroecosystems. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj1999.6351188x>.
- Haddaway, N.R., Hedlund, K., Jackson, L.E., Kätterer, T., Lugato, E., Thomsen, I.K., Jørgensen, H.B., Isberg, P.E., 2017. How does tillage intensity affect soil organic carbon? A systematic review. In: *Environmental Evidence*. BioMed Central. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13750-017-0108-9>.
- Haenlein, M., Kaplan, A.M., 2004. A beginner's guide to partial least squares analysis. *Underst. Stat.* 3, 283–297. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15328031us0304_4.
- Hair, J.F., Risher, J.J., Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C.M., 2019. When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *Eur. Bus. Rev.* 31, 2–24. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-11-2018-0203>.
- Hair, J.F., Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L., Kuppelwieser, V.G., 2014. Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM): an emerging tool in business research. *Eur. Bus. Rev.* 26, 106–121. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-10-2013-0128>.
- Helgason, B.L., Walley, F.L., Germida, J.J., 2009. Fungal and bacterial abundance in long-term no-till and intensive-till soils of the Northern Great Plains. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2007.0392>.
- Hendrix, P.F., Parmelee, R.W., Crossley, D.A., Coleman, D.C., Odum, E.P., Groffman, P. M., 1986. Detritus food webs in conventional and no-tillage agroecosystems. *BioScience* 36. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1310259>.
- Högberg, P., Nordgren, A., Buchmann, N., Taylor, A.F.S., Ekblad, A., Högberg, M.N., Nyberg, G., Ottosson-Löfvenius, M., Read, D.J., 2001. Large-scale forest girdling shows that current photosynthesis drives soil respiration. *Nature* 411, 789–792. <https://doi.org/10.1038/35081058>.
- Huang, M., Jiang, L., Zou, Y., Xu, S., Deng, G., 2013. Changes in soil microbial properties with no-tillage in Chinese cropping systems. *Biol. Fertil. Soils* 49, 373–377. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-013-0778-6>.
- Hydbom, S., Ernfors, M., Birgander, J., Hollander, J., Jensen, E.S., Olsson, P.A., 2017. Reduced tillage stimulated symbiotic fungi and microbial saprotrophs, but did not lead to a shift in the saprotrophic microorganism community structure. *Appl. Soil Ecol.* 119, 104–114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsoil.2017.05.032>.
- Indorf, C., Dyckmans, J., Khan, K.S., Joergensen, R.G., 2011. Optimisation of amino sugar quantification by HPLC in soil and plant hydrolysates. *Biol. Fertil. Soils* 47, 387–396. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-011-0545-5>.
- Irving, T.B., Alptekin, B., Kleven, B., Ané, J.M., 2021. A critical review of 25 years of glomalin research: a better mechanical understanding and robust quantification techniques are required. *New Phytol.* 232, 1572–1581. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nph.17713>.
- IUSS Working Group WRB, 2015. World reference base for soil resources 2014, update 2015: International soil classification system for naming soils and creating legends for soil maps. In: *World Soil Resources Reports No. 106*. FAO, Rome, Italy. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0014479706394902>.
- Joergensen, R.G., 2018. Amino sugars as specific indices for fungal and bacterial residues in soil. *Biol. Fertil. Soils* 54, 559–568. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00374-018-1288-3>.
- Kabir, Z., 2005. Tillage or no-tillage: impact on mycorrhizae. *Can. J. Plant Sci.* 85, 23–29. <https://doi.org/10.4141/P03-160>.
- Kallenbach, C.M., Frey, S.D., Grandy, A.S., 2016. Direct evidence for microbial-derived soil organic matter formation and its ecophysiological controls. *Nat. Commun.* 7, 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms13630>.
- Kallenbach, C.M., Grandy, A.S., Frey, S.D., Diefendorf, A.F., 2015. Microbial physiology and necromass regulate agricultural soil carbon accumulation. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 91, 279–290. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2015.09.005>.
- Keiblinger, K.M., Hall, E.K., Wanek, W., Szukics, U., Hammerle, I., Ellersdorfer, G., Bock, S., Sterflinger, K., Richter, A., Zechmeister-boltenstern, S., 2010. The effect of resource quantity and resource stoichiometry on microbial carbon-use-efficiency. *Fed. Eur. Microbiol. Soc.* 73, 430–440. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1574-6941.2010.00912.x>.
- Kladivko, E.J., 2001. Tillage systems and soil ecology. *Soil Tillage Res.* 61, 61–76. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987\(01\)00179-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987(01)00179-9).
- Korkmaz, S., Goksuluk, D., Zararsiz, G., 2014. MVN: an R package for assessing multivariate normality. *R J.* 6, 151–162. <https://doi.org/10.32614/rj-2014-031>.
- Kumar, D., Shivay, Y.S., Dhar, S., Kumar, C., Prasad, R., 2013. Rhizospheric flora and the influence of agronomic practices on them: a review. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. India Sect. B Biol. Sci.* 83, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40011-012-0059-4>.
- Kuzyakov, Y., Blagodatskaya, E., 2015. Microbial hotspots and hot moments in soil: concept & review. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 83, 184–199. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2015.01.025>.
- Lal, R., 2016. Beyond COP 21: Potential and challenges of the “4 per Thousand” initiative. *J. Soil Water Conserv.* 71 <https://doi.org/10.2489/jswc.71.1.20A>, 20A LP-25A.
- Lal, R., 2013. Soil carbon management and climate change. *Carbon Manag.* 4, 439–462. <https://doi.org/10.4155/cmt.13.31>.
- Lal, R., 2004. Soil carbon sequestration impacts on global climate change and food security. *Science* (80-) 304, 1623–1627. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1097396>.
- Larsen, J., Jaramillo-López, P., Nájera-Rincon, M., González-Esquivel, C.E., 2015. Biotic interactions in the rhizosphere in relation to plant and soil nutrient dynamics. *J. Soil Sci. Plant Nutr.* 15, 449–463. <https://doi.org/10.4067/s0718-95162015005000039>.
- Li, L., Wilson, C.B., He, H., Zhang, X., Zhou, F., Schaeffer, S.M., 2019. Physical, biochemical, and microbial controls on amino sugar accumulation in soils under long-term cover cropping and no-tillage farming. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 135, 369–378. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2019.05.017>.
- Li, N., Xu, Y.Z., Han, X.Z., He, H.B., Zhang, X.dong, Zhang, B., 2015. Fungi contribute more than bacteria to soil organic matter through necromass accumulation under different agricultural practices during the early pedogenesis of a Mollisol. *Eur. J. Soil Biol.* 67, 51–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejsobi.2015.02.002>.
- Liang, C., 2020. Soil microbial carbon pump: mechanism and appraisal. *Soil Ecol. Lett.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42832-020-0052-4>.
- Liang, C., Amelung, W., Lehmann, J., Kästner, M., 2019. Quantitative assessment of microbial necromass contribution to soil organic matter. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 25, 3578–3590. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14781>.
- Liang, C., Balser, T.C., 2011. Microbial production of recalcitrant organic matter in global soils: implications for productivity and climate policy. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* 9, 75. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrmicro2386-c1>.
- Liang, C., Schimel, J.P., Jastrow, J.D., 2017. The importance of anabolism in microbial control over soil carbon storage. *Nat. Microbiol.* 2 <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmicrobiol.2017.105>.
- Mathew, R.P., Feng, Y., Githinji, L., Ankumah, R., Balkcom, K.S., 2012. Impact of no-tillage and conventional tillage systems on soil microbial communities. *Appl. Environ. Soil Sci.* 2012 <https://doi.org/10.1155/2012/548620>.
- Minasny, B., Malone, B.P., McBratney, A.B., Angers, D.A., Arrouays, D., Chambers, A., Chaplot, V., Chen, Z.S., Cheng, K., Das, B.S., Field, D.J., Gimona, A., Hedley, C.B., Hong, S.Y., Mandal, B., Marchant, B.P., Martin, M., McConkey, B.G., Mulder, V.L., O'Rourke, S., Richer-de-Forges, A.C., Odeh, I., Padoiran, J., Paustian, K., Pan, G., Poggio, L., Savin, I., Stolbovov, V., Stockmann, U., Sulaeman, Y., Tsui, C.C., Vágen, T.G., van Wesemael, B., Winowiecki, L., 2017. Soil carbon 4 per mille. *Geoderma* 292, 59–86. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2017.01.002>.
- Molope, M.B., Grieve, I.C., Page, E.R., 1987. Contributions by fungi and bacteria to aggregate stability of cultivated soils. *J. Soil Sci.* 38 <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2389.1987.tb02124.x>.
- Monecke, A., Leisch, F., 2012. SemPLS: structural equation modeling using partial least squares. *J. Stat. Softw.* 48 <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v048.i03>.
- Morris, N.L., Miller, P.C.H., Orson, J.H., Froud-Williams, R.J., 2010. The adoption of non-inversion tillage systems in the United Kingdom and the agronomic impact on soil, crops and the environment—a review. *Soil Tillage Res.* 108, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2010.03.004>.
- Ogle, S.M., Breidt, F.J., Paustian, K., 2005. Agricultural management impacts on soil organic carbon storage under moist and dry climatic conditions of temperate and tropical regions. *Biogeochemistry* 72, 87–121. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10533-004-0360-2>.
- Pagliari, M., Vignozzi, N., Pellegrini, S., 2004. Soil structure and the effect of management practices. *Soil Tillage Res.* 79, 131–143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2004.07.002>.
- Parsons, J.W., 1981. Chemistry and distribution of amino sugars in soils and soil organisms. *Soil Biochem.* 5, 197–227.
- Pathan, S.I., Ceccherini, M.T., Sunseri, F., Lupini, A., 2020. Rhizosphere as hotspot for plant-soil-microbe interaction. In: *Carbon And Nitrogen Cycling in Soil*. Springer, Singapore, pp. 17–43. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-7264-3_2.
- Paustian, K., Lehmann, J., Ogle, S., Reay, D., Robertson, G.P., Smith, P., 2016. Climate-smart soils. *Nature* 532, 49–57. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature17174>.
- Peixoto, D.S., Silva, L.C.M., Melo, L.B.B., Azevedo, R.P., Araújo, B.C.L., Carvalho, T.S., Moreira, S.G., Curi, N., Silva, B.M., 2020. Occasional tillage in no-tillage systems: a global meta-analysis. *Sci. Total Environ.* 745, 140887 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.140887>.
- Piepho, H.P., Büchse, A., Richter, C., 2004. A mixed modelling approach for randomized experiments with repeated measures. *J. Agron. Crop Sci.* 190, 230–247.
- Pires, L.F., Borges, J.A.R., Rosa, J.A., Cooper, M., Heck, R.J., Passoni, S., Roque, W.L., 2017. Soil structure changes induced by tillage systems. *Soil Tillage Res.* 165, 66–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2016.07.010>.
- Pirmoradian, N., Sepaskhah, A.R., Hajabbasi, M.A., 2005. Application of fractal theory to quantify soil aggregate stability as influenced by tillage treatments. *Biosyst. Eng.* 90, 227–234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2004.11.002>.
- Rasmussen, K.J., 1999. Impact of ploughless soil tillage on yield and soil quality: a Scandinavian review. *Soil Tillage Res.* 53, 3–14. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987\(99\)00072-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-1987(99)00072-0).
- Ravand, H., Purya, B., 2016. Partial least squares structural equation modeling with R. *Pract. Assessment. Res. Eval.* 21, 1–16.

- Reichert, J.M., Suzuki, L.E.A.S., Reinert, D.J., Horn, R., Håkansson, I., 2009. Reference bulk density and critical degree-of-compactness for no-till crop production in subtropical highly weathered soils. *Soil Tillage Res.* 102, 242–254. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2008.07.002>.
- Řezáčová, V., Czakó, A., Stehlík, M., Mayerová, M., Šimon, T., Smatanová, M., Madaras, M., 2021. Organic fertilization improves soil aggregation through increases in abundance of eubacteria and products of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi. *Sci. Rep.* 11, 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-91653-x>.
- Rillig, M.C., Mummey, D.L., 2006. Mycorrhizas and soil structure. *New Phytol.* 171, 41–53. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-8137.2006.01750.x>.
- Rousk, J., Bååth, E., Brookes, P.C., Lauber, C.L., Lozupone, C., Caporaso, J.G., Knight, R., Fierer, N., 2010. Soil bacterial and fungal communities across a pH gradient in an arable soil. *ISME J.* 4, 1340–1351. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ismej.2010.58>.
- Sae-Tun, O., Maftukhah, R., Noller, C., Remlinger, V.I., Meyer-Laker, V., Sørensen, A.C. T., Sustic, D., Socianu, S.I., Bernardini, L.G., Mentler, A., Keiblinger, K.M., 2020. Comparison of commonly used extraction methods for ergosterol in soil samples. *Int. Agrophys.* 34, 425–432. <https://doi.org/10.31545/INTAGR/127707>.
- Sanaullah, M., Usman, M., Wakeel, A., Cheema, S.A., Ashraf, I., Farooq, M., 2020. Terrestrial ecosystem functioning affected by agricultural management systems: a review. *Soil Tillage Res.* 196 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2019.104464>.
- Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C.M., Hair, J.F., 2017. Partial least squares structural equation modeling. In: Homburg, C., Klarmann, M., Vomberg, A. (Eds.), *Handbook of Market Research*. Springer International Publishing, pp. 1–40. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-05542-8>.
- Sauvadet, M., Lashermes, G., Alavoine, G., Recous, S., Chauvat, M., Maron, P.A., Bertrand, I., 2018. High carbon use efficiency and low priming effect promote soil C stabilization under reduced tillage. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 123, 64–73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2018.04.026>.
- Schlesinger, W.H., Amundson, R., 2019. Managing for soil carbon sequestration: let's get realistic. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 25, 386–389. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14478>.
- Schomakers, J., Mentler, A., Mayer, H., 2014. Determination of dissolved organic carbon in soils with uV spectroscopy, ultrasonic dispersion pre-treatment and separation with size exclusion chromatography. *Span. J. Soil Sci.* 4, 127–142. <https://doi.org/10.3232/SJSS.2014.V4.N2.01>.
- Senthamarai Kannan, K., Manoj, K., 2015. Outlier detection in multivariate data. *Appl. Math. Sci.* 9, 2317–2324. <https://doi.org/10.12988/ams.2015.53213>.
- Shen, X., Wang, L., Yang, Q., Xiu, W., Li, G., Zhao, J., Zhang, G., 2021. Dynamics of soil organic carbon and labile carbon fractions in soil aggregates affected by different tillage managements. *Sustainability* 13, 1541. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13031541>.
- Six, J., Bossuyt, H., Degryze, S., Denef, K., 2004. A history of research on the link between (micro)aggregates, soil biota, and soil organic matter dynamics. *Soil Tillage Res.* 79, 7–31. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2004.03.008>.
- Six, J., Elliott, E.T., Paustian, K., 2000. Soil macroaggregate turnover and microaggregate formation: a mechanism for C sequestration under no-tillage agriculture. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 32, 2099–2103. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717\(00\)00179-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-0717(00)00179-6).
- Six, J., Frey, S.D., Thiet, R.K., Batten, K.M., 2006. Bacterial and fungal contributions to carbon sequestration in agroecosystems. *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. J.* 70, 555–569. <https://doi.org/10.2136/sssaj2004.0347>.
- Soares, M., Rousk, J., 2019. Microbial growth and carbon use efficiency in soil: links to fungal-bacterial dominance, SOC-quality and stoichiometry. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 131, 195–205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2019.01.010>.
- Sokol, N.W., Bradford, M.A., 2019. Microbial formation of stable soil carbon is more efficient from belowground than aboveground input. *Nat. Geosci.* 12, 46–53. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-018-0258-6>.
- Sokol, N.W., Sanderman, J., Bradford, M.A., 2019. Pathways of mineral-associated soil organic matter formation: integrating the role of plant carbon source, chemistry, and point of entry. *Glob. Chang. Biol.* 25, 12–24. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14482>.
- Spedding, T.A., Hamel, C., Mehuys, G.R., Madramootoo, C.A., 2004. Soil microbial dynamics in maize-growing soil under different tillage and residue management systems. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 36, 499–512. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2003.10.026>.
- Strickland, M.S., Rousk, J., 2010. Considering fungal: bacterial dominance in soils - methods, controls, and ecosystem implications. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 42, 1385–1395. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2010.05.007>.
- Tagar, A.A., Adamowski, J., Memon, M.S., Do, M.C., Mashori, A.S., Soomro, A.S., Bhayo, W.A., 2020. Soil fragmentation and aggregate stability as affected by conventional tillage implements and relations with fractal dimensions. *Soil Tillage Res.* 197, 104494 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2019.104494>.
- Totsche, K.U., Amelung, W., Gerzabek, M.H., Guggenberger, G., Klumpp, E., Knief, C., Lehdorff, E., Mikutta, R., Peth, S., Prechtel, A., Ray, N., Kögel-Knabner, I., 2018. Microaggregates in soils. *J. Plant Nutr. Soil Sci.* 181, 104–136. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jpln.201600451>.
- Van Der Heijden, M.G.A., Bardgett, R.D., Van Straalen, N.M., 2008. The unseen majority: soil microbes as drivers of plant diversity and productivity in terrestrial ecosystems. *Ecol. Lett.* 11, 296–310. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1461-0248.2007.01139.x>.
- van Groenigen, K.J., Bloem, J., Bååth, E., Boeckx, P., Rousk, J., Bodé, S., Forristal, D., Jones, M.B., 2010. Abundance, production and stabilization of microbial biomass under conventional and reduced tillage. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 42, 48–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2009.09.023>.
- Veloso, M.G., Angers, D.A., Chantigny, M.H., Bayer, C., 2020. Carbon accumulation and aggregation are mediated by fungi in a subtropical soil under conservation agriculture. *Geoderma* 363, 114159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2019.114159>.
- Wallander, H., Ekblad, A., Godbold, D.L., Johnson, D., Bahr, A., Baldrian, P., Björk, R.G., Kieliszewska-Rokicka, B., Kjeller, R., Kraigher, H., Plassard, C., Rudawska, M., 2013. Evaluation of methods to estimate production, biomass and turnover of ectomycorrhizal mycelium in forests soils - a review. *Soil Biol. Biochem.* 57, 1034–1047. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soilbio.2012.08.027>.
- Wang, Z., Liu, L., Chen, Q., Wen, X., Liu, Y., Han, J., Liao, Y., 2017. Conservation tillage enhances the stability of the rhizosphere bacterial community responding to plant growth. *Agron. Sustain. Dev.* 37, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-017-0454-6>.
- Weninger, T., Kreiselmeier, J., Chandrasekar, P., Julich, S., Feger, K.H., Schwärzel, K., Bodner, G., Schwen, A., 2019. Effects of tillage intensity on pore system and physical quality of silt-textured soils detected by multiple methods. *Soil Res.* 57, 703–711. <https://doi.org/10.1071/SR18347>.
- Wright, S.F., Upadhyaya, A., 1998. A survey of soils for aggregate stability and glomalin, a glycoprotein produced by hyphae of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi. *Plant Soil* 198, 97–107. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1004347701584>.
- Xu, X., Schimel, J.P., Thornton, P.E., Song, X., Yuan, F., Goswami, S., 2014. Substrate and environmental controls on microbial assimilation of soil organic carbon: a framework for Earth system models. *Ecol. Lett.* 17, 547–555. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ele.12254>.
- Yang, Y., He, C., Huang, L., Ban, Y., Tang, M., 2017. The effects of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi on glomalin-related soil protein distribution, aggregate stability and their relationships with soil properties at different soil depths in lead-zinc contaminated area. *PLoS One* 12. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0182264>.
- ZAMG-Zentralanstalt für Meteorologie und Geodynamik, 2020. Klimamittel [WWW Document]. <https://www.zamg.ac.at/cms/de/klima/klimaubersichten/klimamittel-1971-2000> accessed 8.6.20.